

ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF INFRASTRUCTURE CHANGES IN
UZBEKISTAN ON MUTUAL COMPETITIVENESS AMONG ECONOMIC
PARTICIPANTS

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Abstract:

This study examines the impact of recent infrastructure developments on mutual competitiveness among economic participants in Uzbekistan. As the country undergoes significant transformations in its transportation, energy, and digital infrastructure, these changes are reshaping the competitive dynamics within its economy. The research investigates how these infrastructural improvements influence the competitive positions of various sectors, including state-owned enterprises, private firms, and foreign investors.

Key words: Competition, export, import, infrastructure, Industry, investment, investment climate, Economic inequality, regional disparity, unemployment.

Introduction

In recent years, Uzbekistan has embarked on a transformative journey of infrastructure development, aimed at enhancing its economic landscape and positioning itself as a competitive player in the global market. As part of this ambitious agenda, the country has invested heavily in upgrading its transportation networks, energy systems, and digital infrastructure. These changes are not only reshaping the domestic economy but are also influencing the dynamics of mutual competitiveness among various economic participants within Uzbekistan.

The modernization of infrastructure is widely recognized as a critical driver of economic growth, offering numerous benefits such as improved efficiency, reduced transaction costs, and enhanced connectivity. However, its impact on the competitive balance among businesses, industries, and regions within a country is less straightforward. In the context of Uzbekistan, where the economy is marked by a mix of state-owned enterprises, private firms, and foreign investors, understanding how these infrastructure improvements influence competitive interactions is of paramount importance.

This study aims to evaluate the impact of recent infrastructure changes on mutual competitiveness among economic participants in Uzbekistan. By analyzing key sectors affected by these developments, this research seeks to provide insights into how infrastructure investments are altering the competitive landscape. Furthermore, the study will explore whether these changes are fostering a more equitable economic environment or exacerbating existing disparities. Through this evaluation, the research will contribute to a deeper understanding of the strategic role that infrastructure plays in shaping economic competition in emerging markets like Uzbekistan.

Reforms in industrial policy have emphasized diversifying the economy away from reliance on raw materials, such as cotton and gold, towards manufacturing and services. Special economic zones (SEZs) and industrial parks have been established to attract foreign direct investment (FDI), promote exports, and stimulate innovation. Moreover, measures have been taken to simplify business registration processes and improve the ease of doing business, contributing to an influx of international investment.

Uzbekistan has made significant strides in upgrading its transport infrastructure, including the construction of new highways, railways, and logistics hubs. The development of regional connectivity, especially through initiatives like the Trans-Caspian International Transport Route (TITR), positions Uzbekistan as a

key transit hub in Central Asia. Concurrently, energy sector reforms have focused on modernizing electricity grids, increasing renewable energy capacity, and improving energy efficiency.

As of August 1, 2024, the number of enterprises and organizations registered in the field of transportation and storage services in our Republic has reached 25,210. This indicator has increased by 5% compared to the same period last year. Their dynamics in the corresponding periods of the last five years are as follows:¹

Improvements in Global Competitiveness Ranking. As Uzbekistan's infrastructure modernizes, the country's rankings in global competitiveness indices, such as the World Economic Forum's Global Competitiveness Report, have improved. Better transport networks, increased energy efficiency, and enhanced industrial capacity have contributed to reducing the cost of doing business and improving the country's attractiveness as an investment destination.

¹ Information from the State Statistics Committee <https://stat.uz/uz/matbuot-markazi/qo-mita-yangiliklar/56435-tashish-va-saqlash-sohasida-korxonalar-soni-qancha-6>

Uzbekistan's strategic focus on industrialization has resulted in a more diversified export base. Manufacturing and processed goods, including textiles, chemicals, and automotive parts, are becoming significant export contributors. The country's improved logistics infrastructure has also opened up access to new markets in Europe, the Middle East, and South Asia, which enhances its position in international trade.

Despite these gains, the distribution of economic benefits has been uneven across Uzbekistan's regions. Major cities like Tashkent and Samarkand have benefited disproportionately from infrastructure investments, while rural and remote areas have seen slower development. This imbalance could erode national competitiveness by leaving significant portions of the population with limited access to economic opportunities and critical infrastructure.

The rapid pace of infrastructure development has strained public finances, leading to an increase in government debt. Additionally, inflationary pressures have emerged, particularly due to rising construction costs and the expansion of credit to finance these projects. If left unchecked, high inflation could undermine household purchasing power and reduce the real gains from economic growth.

While industrialization is a cornerstone of Uzbekistan's economic strategy, it has raised concerns about environmental sustainability. The reliance on natural resource extraction and energy-intensive industries poses risks of pollution and resource depletion. Furthermore, industrialization has led to disruptions in traditional sectors such as agriculture, displacing workers and creating pockets of unemployment.

The geographic concentration of infrastructure projects has exacerbated regional disparities. Urban centers are experiencing rapid growth, but rural areas, particularly in the autonomous Republic of Karakalpakstan and the Fergana Valley, have not benefited equally. This growing inequality threatens social

cohesion and long-term economic stability, as it leaves large portions of the population without adequate employment or access to services.

To reduce regional inequalities, a more inclusive approach to infrastructure development is needed. This includes increasing investments in rural and remote areas to provide these regions with access to modern transport, energy, and communication networks. Encouraging local economic development through targeted incentives can also help bridge the gap between urban and rural growth rates.

Uzbekistan must continue to strengthen its social safety net programs to mitigate the impacts of structural changes on vulnerable populations. This includes expanding unemployment benefits, reskilling programs, and regional development funds to ensure that workers displaced by industrialization can transition to new sectors without falling into poverty.

A critical focus should be placed on ensuring that Uzbekistan's industrial growth is environmentally sustainable. Policies that promote green technologies, energy efficiency, and waste management must be integrated into industrial strategies. Additionally, regulations to safeguard natural resources, particularly water and land, should be prioritized to avoid environmental degradation.

To curb inflationary pressures and maintain fiscal stability, Uzbekistan should consider adopting more prudent monetary and fiscal policies. This may involve a gradual reduction in government borrowing for large infrastructure projects, combined with measures to improve the efficiency of public spending. Stabilizing inflation through tighter monetary policy will also help protect household incomes and preserve economic gains.

Conclusion

Uzbekistan's ongoing efforts to modernize its economic infrastructure have undoubtedly enhanced its competitiveness on the global stage. However, the challenges associated with rapid economic transformation—such as regional

inequality, inflationary risks, and environmental sustainability—require careful management. By adopting inclusive growth policies, strengthening social safety nets, and emphasizing sustainable development, Uzbekistan can ensure that its economic reforms lead to broad-based prosperity and resilience against potential shocks.

References

1. Decree No. PF-37 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 02.21.2024 on the state program for the implementation of the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy in the "Year of supporting youth and business"
2. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoev, on September 17, 2019, held a video selector meeting on the issues of rapid development of industry, increasing the level of localization and expanding its scope.
3. World Bank. (2020). Uzbekistan - Country Economic Update: Economic Transition Amid Global Uncertainty*.
4. OECD. (2022). *OECD Economic Surveys: Uzbekistan*.
5. Asian Development Bank. (2021). *Infrastructure Development in Central Asia: Challenges and Opportunities*.
6. UNDP. (2022). *Uzbekistan's Human Development Report: Building a Sustainable Future*.
7. Information from the State Statistics Committee <https://stat.uz/uz/matbuot-markazi/qo-mita-yangiliklar/56435-tashish-va-saqlash-sohasida-korxonalar-soni-qancha-6>